

Igbo

also known as “Ibo”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Syncretic Religions, African Religions, Religious Group

The Igbo (spelled “Ibo” by British colonialists; Amadiume, 2003) live across Nigeria, and are united by shared linguistic and cultural traditions. There is no central political authority among the Igbo; the largest social unit is the village-group, bound together by ties but each village is functionally independent. In fact, there is “no individual of outstanding power or authority either directly in things spiritual or indirectly in things secular (Green, 1964:49).” Although there are not official religious leaders among the Igbo, there are two types of religious practitioners: priests and dibeas. Hereditary priests observe taboos and lead ceremonies, but are otherwise viewed as “ordinary” members of the community (Green, 1964:53). A dibeas, on the other hand, undergoes training and initiation rites to become a specialist in the professions of diviner and/or doctor-magician. Various types of supernatural beings are present. There is belief in a supreme high god who is largely viewed as an otiose creator deity overseeing the world from above, and is not typically worshipped directly. Additionally present are the spirits of deceased humans, and ancestor worship appears to be the concern/responsibility of individual households and families. Several non-human spirits are also present, including village and village-group deities. Larger-scale rituals/ceremonies/celebrations are present, such as the annual rites surrounding the worship of the village-group deity. It is important to note the presence of Christian influence among the Igbo, beginning with the arrival of missionaries in the mid 1800’s. The religious realm of Igbo life is not distinct, but is bound in the functioning of the society as a whole. Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society. This entry focuses specifically on the Eastern Isu-Ana division, Owerri, or Southern Igbo, around the time of 1935.

Date Range: 1910 CE - 1940 CE

Region: Isu-Ana division, Owerri or Southern Ibo, Nigeria

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Nigeria

Isu-Ana division, Owerri or Southern Ibo, Nigeria, ca. 1935

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

– Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization:

Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.

– Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ff26-004>

– Source 1 Description: Uchendu, Victor Chikezie. "Igbo Of Southeast Nigeria." *Case Studies In Cultural Anthropology*, Rinehart and Winston, 1965, pp. xiii, 111

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ff26-003>

– Source 2 Description: Green, M. M. (Margaret Mackeson). *Ibo Village Affairs*. Praeger, 1964

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ff26-001>

– Source 3 Description: Forde, Cyril Daryll, and Gwilym Iwan Jones. "Ibo (Igbo)." *Ibo And Ibibio-Speaking Peoples Of South-Eastern Nigeria*, By Daryll Forde And G. I. Jones, Published for the International African Institute by Oxford University Press, 1950, pp. 9–65

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ff26-000>

– Source 1 Description: Amadiume, Ifi. Culture Summary: Igbo. HRAF, 2003,

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "It was in 1857 that Bishop Crowther successfully established a Church Missionary Society mission at Onitsha. The Roman Catholic Mission followed in 1885. Onitsha thus became the religious and educational center of these two great proselytizing missions as well as the base for British military penetration into northern Igboland. Although the missionaries enjoyed the protective power and the military prestige of the advancing colonial power, it was the 'mystery of the written word'—the psychology of the 'bush schools' founded by them—rather than military might or the 'content of the Bible' which assured their success among the Igbo" (Uchendu, 1965:4).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), was originally coded as 3.75, which is between the original codes of 3 ("internal warfare seems to occur once every 2 years"), and 4 ("internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season"). Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), indicates that "External warfare seems to be absent or rare" (original code 1). Note that SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, codes the Igbo as "inferred to be unpacified because warfare frequency is greater than or equal to 3." Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the recruitment of new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: There is no official leadership position in either the political or religious realm. The religion has official political support in the sense that these two realms are bound together. Moreover, village unity (and village-group unity, see Green, 1964:12) comes from shared religious beliefs. "It would seem that in Ogbudi we have an undoubted symbol of village unity...In Ibo society political authority is often little defined and is not centralised in any one figure like a Chief who can become a symbol of the people's unity. But it may be that in Ogbudi the village finds a personification of its identity, particularly in its legal or political aspect, that one must not underestimate" (Green, 1964:27).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority on the Igbo, Green, (1964) did not record a specific population estimate, but rather an estimate of the population density at 450-1000 people per square mile (see Green, 1964:xiii,33).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "...these innumerable small units, the village-groups, are held together by no central or coordinating authority. But each one of them is linked, not by political but by social ties, to the units round it. An understanding of the Ibo system of exogamy is, in this connection, essential. Inter-marriage creates a network of ties by which the cells of Ibo society, though not united by any central governmental authority, nor arranged in any political hierarchy, are none the less inter-linked horizontally each with its neighbours by the social bonds of intermarriage. There are also economic links, but these appear to be, in part at any rate, dependent on the fact of intermarriage" (Green, 1964:8). "When we turn to the supernatural sphere and ask what element of authority it supplies in

village affairs, we find, as in the economic sphere, that there was no individual of outstanding power or authority either directly in things spiritual or indirectly in things secular. There was indeed a hereditary priestly family, Umu Nwacuku, said to have been chosen in the old days by the guardian deity of the village, Ezeala Ogbudi, for the service of his cult. The head of the family was specifically the priest, though his brothers were also involved. They performed the annual religious rites of the seventh month, done, village by village, throughout Agbaja...During the rest of the year the priest officiated for anyone who had been told by a diviner to sacrifice to the village spirit with the help of the priest" (Green, 1964:49). "The two sets of people who pre-eminently deal with the supernatural side of life are the priests and the nde dibe, and it is important to be clear as to the marked difference between them. A priest, though he observes taboos and performs ceremonies, is yet what one might call an ordinary member of society. A dibe, on the other hand, though he still joins in many of the generalised activities of farming, trading, house-building and the like, is none the less a specialist, a member of a profession which entails hard and costly training and initiation, and complicated and often arduous technical activities" (Green, 1964:53).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirit (Ogbudi, guardian spirit of the village) has a shrine in the village market place and also outside the house-group of the priestly family of the cult. A less important spirit, Opara Iyi, the offspring of Ogbudi, has its shrine in a thicket near Umu Nwa Ebodim, many of whose osu are dedicated to it" (Green, 1964:26).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "For the Igbo, death is a necessary precondition for joining the ancestors, just as reincarnation is necessary for the peopling of the temporal segment of the lineage" (Uchendu, 1965:12).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "In the Igbo conception, the world of the 'dead' is a world full of activities; its inhabitants manifest in their behavior and thought processes that they are 'living.' The dead continue their lineage system; they are organized in lineages with patrilineal emphasis just as are those on earth. The principle of seniority makes the ancestors the head of the lineage; it gives the lineage its stability and continuity" (Uchendu, 1965:12).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "In the Igbo view, there is a constant interaction between the dead and the living: the dead are reincarnated, death making the transition from the corporeal to the incorporeal life of the ancestors possible" (Uchendu, 1965:12).

In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "The Igbo idea that the ancestors and other deceased members come back to 'temporal life' is rooted in their theory of reincarnation. Belief in reincarnation gives the Igbo hope of realizing their frustrated status goals in the next cycle of life" (Uchendu, 1965:102).

In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: "Transmigration, on the other hand, is regarded as the greatest possible punishment for the incestuous, the murderer, the witch, and the sorcerer. 'Ilɔdigh uwa na mmadu' 'May you not reincarnate in the human form'—is a great curse for the Igbo" (Uchendu, 1965:102).

In form of an inanimate object(s):

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased are typically buried. See questions below for more details.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "It is the prayer of the Igbo to die among their agnates and be buried in their ancestral land. Normally the corpse of a married woman who died in her husband's home is brought back to be buried among her kinsmen. But if a woman had achieved a high social status and had expressed the desire to be buried in her husband's home, a 'death duty' is usually paid to her agnates" (Uchendu, 1965:65).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

Notes: Unspecified

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

Notes: Unspecified

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– I don't know

Notes: Unspecified

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "Death is not considered enough punishment for an Igbo who has offended against Ala [Earth-Goddess]. He is denied ground burial, the worst social humiliation for any Igbo" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "It is believed that the spirit of the dead person wanders about restless and homeless until the final mortuary rites, 'second burial', are performed, several months or even years after the death. If these rites are too long delayed, the anger of the deceased's spirit is believed to make itself felt through mishaps to the family" (Forde and Jones, 1950: 27). According to SCCS variable 1850 (secondary bone/body treatment: original scale), "secondary contact with the body or bones is the preferred means of disposal for all or nearly all adult members of the society" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence on the details of burial practices.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence on the details of burial practices.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for available information on formal burials.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence on the details of burial practices.

↳ In cemetery:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence on the details of burial practices.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence on the details of burial practices.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "A man is generally buried beneath the floor of his hut or compound" (Forde and Jones, 1950:27).

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Individual Tomb

Notes: "But if a woman had achieved a high social status and had expressed the desire to be buried in her husband's home, a 'death duty' is usually paid to her agnates. It is then the duty of her sons to make a cement tomb (a symbol of high social status) for her" (Uchendu, 1965:65).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A variety of supernatural beings are present among the Igbo. See questions below for more details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The idea of a creator of all things is focal to Igbo theology. They believe in a supreme god, a high god, who is all good...The Igbo high god is a withdrawn god. He is a god who has finished all active works of creation and keeps watch over his creatures from a distance. The Igbo high god is not worshiped directly" (Uchendu, 1965:94). "The high god is conceived of in different roles. In his creative role, he is called Chinεκε, Chi-Okike (Chi-God; Okike—that creates). To distinguish him from other minor gods he is called Chukwu—the great or the high god. As the creator of everything, he is called Chukwu Abiama, while as the pillar that supports the heavens, he is called Agalaba ji igwe. The sky is regarded as his place of residence and people invoke his name as Chi-di-n'elu—'God who lives above.'" (Uchendu, 1965:95).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified, but ethnographer refers to the high god as "he".

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "As the creator of everything, he is called Chukwu Abiama, while as the pillar that supports the heavens, he is called Agalaba ji igwε. The sky is regarded as his place of residence and people invoke his name as Chi-di-n'εlu—"God who lives above." (Uchendu, 1965:95).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: (Uchendu, 1965:95)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The Igbo do not possess a monarch.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The Igbo do not possess a monarch.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the Igbo] believe in a supreme god, a high god, who is all good" (Uchendu, 1965:94).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Igbo high god is a withdrawn god. He is a god who has finished all active works of creation and keeps watch over his creatures from a distance" (Uchendu, 1965:94).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "He [the high god] seldom interferes in the affairs of men, a characteristic which sets him apart from all other deities, spirits, and ancestors. He is a satisfied god who is not jealous of the prosperity of man on earth" (Uchendu, 1965:94).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Although the high god may be distant and withdrawn, he is not completely separated from the affairs of men. He is still the great father, the source of all good. He interacts with each Igbo during each reincarnation cycle. He sometimes intervenes in

favor of the living but not as quickly as suppliants would like" (Uchendu, 1965:95).

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: "The Igbo high god is not worshiped directly. There is neither shrine nor priest dedicated to his service. He gets no direct sacrifice from the living but is conceived as [Page 95] the ultimate receiver of all sacrifice made to the minor deities" (Uchendu, 1965:94).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ancestors occupy a special place in Igbo religious practice. The Igbo conceive of their ancestors as the invisible segment of the lineage. The ancestors are 'honored' and not 'worshiped' in the strict sense. The ancestral honor is a religion based on reciprocity. There is a loving reverence for the deceased ancestors, who are expected to come back to reincarnate and 'do to the living members what they did for them'" (Uchendu, 1965:102). Previously human spirits are not described in substantial ethnographic detail.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Besides the high god, there are other minor gods called nature gods, sometimes described as kind, hospitable and industrious; at other times, they are conceived of as fraudulent, treacherous, unmerciful, and envious. They are, in general, subject to human passions and weaknesses. But they can be controlled, manipulated, and, in fact, used to further human interests" (Uchendu, 1965:95).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "She [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ—alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger. Incest is a good example. As the custodian of Igbo morality, ala must take action to save the community" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

— Yes

Notes: "But she [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not punish in haste; she gives many signals of her displeasure. Quite reluctantly, after many unheeded warnings, ala may kill by bouncing the wicked on the ground until they are dead. She does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ—alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Notes: "Though the minor gods are not normally ranked in importance the Igbo regard ala, the earth-goddess, nearest to them, with the possible exception of their ancestors. Ala is an earth-goddess, a great mother. She is the spirit of fertility. She increases the fertility of man and the productivity of the land. Without her, life would be impossible for the Igbo, who attach much sentiment to the land" (Uchendu, 1965:95). "Anyanwu is the sun-god. He makes crops and trees grow" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

— Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

— Yes

Notes: "In the cult of the guardian deity of the village is a further force in the religious sphere which both emphasises the identity and makes for the unity of the village. This guardian spirit, Ezεala Ogbudi in its male aspect, and Lɔlɔ Ogbudi in its female, is an offspring of the central deity of all Agbaja, just as the original founder of the village is a son of the original ancestor of all Agbaja. Human and supernatural organisation follow closely similar lines and the supernatural helps to validate and support the human" (Green, 1964:26).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

— Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detailed information on supernatural monitoring among the Igbo.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "But the supernatural sanctions which stress the virtues of filial piety and mutual responsibility among kinsmen so far as the dead are concerned cannot fail also to promote them among the living" (Green, 1964:52-53).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "But she [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not punish in haste; she gives many signals of her displeasure. Quite reluctantly, after many unheeded warnings, ala may kill by bouncing the wicked on the ground until they are dead. She does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ–alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: "Aha Njoku is a powerful spirit respected by the Igbo. Women call her nwanji dim—a co-wife. She acts as a social sanction which controls the behavior of women in the home, the farm, and the ɔba—a storage place for yams. Women are obliged not to throw away yams in anger, an act that offends aha njoku. But if they do and subsequently eat yams without appeasing aha njoku, it is believed they will have dysentery or cholera. Out of respect for the yam spirit, fighting is not allowed on the farm. Quarreling on the farm must be appeased, and an egg is usually broken on the spot to ask for forgiveness" (Uchendu, 1965:98-99).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "She [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ–alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger. Incest is a good example. As the custodian of Igbo morality, ala must take action to save the community" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: "She [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ–alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger. Incest is a good example. As the custodian of Igbo morality, ala must take action to save the community" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: "Later on, Mgbɔkwθ, a woman married in Umueke, explained that if anyone used bad

magic against a member of the village, Ogbudi [village guardian deity] would cause the magic to turn against its user" (Green, 1964:27).

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: "Out of respect for the yam spirit, fighting is not allowed on the farm. Quarreling on the farm must be appeased, and an egg is usually broken on the spot to ask for forgiveness" (Uchendu, 1965:98-99).

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "Other spirits include *ekwu*—the hearth spirit, which is women's domestic spirit. Children who neglect their aged mothers are-cursed on the *ekwu*" (Uchendu, 1965:100).

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: "But it was perhaps Ogbudi [village guardian deity] that chiefly stood to the village as its supernatural protector and the guardian of its laws. I had not been in the place a week before [an informant] told me that Ogbudi would kill anyone who was guilty of stealing" (Green, 1964:26-27).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Multiple supernatural beings are described as the agents of supernatural punishment. See questions below for more details. Also see Uchendu, 1965:52-53, 96, 100; and Green, 1964:26-27.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Multiple supernatural beings are described as the agents of supernatural punishment. See Uchendu, 1965:52-53, 96, 100; and Green, 1964:26-27.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Multiple supernatural beings are described as the agents of supernatural punishment. See Uchendu, 1965:52-53, 96, 100; and Green, 1964:26-27.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Multiple supernatural beings are described as the agents of supernatural punishment. See Uchendu, 1965:52-53, 96, 100; and Green, 1964:26-27.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding the reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "But she [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not punish in haste; she gives many signals of her displeasure. Quite reluctantly, after many unheeded warnings, ala may kill by bouncing the wicked on the ground until they are dead. She does not kill for minor offenses. Only such offenses classed as nsɔ–alθ (taboo)—warrant her anger" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: "Other spirits include ekwu—the hearth spirit, which is women's domestic spirit. Children who neglect their aged mothers are-cursed on the ekwu" (Uchendu, 1965:100).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Transmigration, on the other hand, is regarded as the greatest possible punishment for the incestuous, the murderer, the witch, and the sorcerer. 'Ildigh uwa na mmadu' 'May you not reincarnate in the human form'—is a great curse for the Igbo. The reincarnation of those who violated taboos is usually said to be inauspicious. They are born either feet first or with teeth or as members of a twin set—all of which are in themselves taboo" (Uchendu, 1965:102).

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: "Transmigration, on the other hand, is regarded as the greatest possible punishment for the incestuous, the murderer, the witch, and the sorcerer. 'Ildigh uwa na mmadu' 'May you not reincarnate in the human form'—is a great curse for the Igbo. The reincarnation of those who violated taboos is usually said to be inauspicious. They are born either feet first or with teeth or as members of a twin set—all of which are in themselves taboo" (Uchendu, 1965:102).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment is present, but not described in extensive ethnographic detail. See questions below for available information.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Aha Njoku is a powerful spirit respected by the Igbo. Women call her nwanyi dim—a co-wife. She acts as a social sanction which controls the behavior of women in the home, the farm, and the oba—a storage place for yams. Women are obliged not to throw away yams in anger, an act that offends aha njoku. But if they do and subsequently eat yams without appeasing aha njoku, it is believed they will have dysentery or cholera" (Uchendu, 1965:98-99).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "But she [Ala, the Earth-Goddess] does not punish in haste; she gives many signals of her displeasure. Quite reluctantly, after many unheeded warnings, ala may kill by bouncing the wicked on the ground until they are dead. She does not kill for minor offenses" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: "Ala helps the Igbo with many things. They ask her for children, for prosperity in trade, and for increase in livestock. As the source of strength, she must be notified before her children go to war" (Uchendu, 1965:96).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Legal rules are of two main classes and are recognised as such. There are those which might be called ordinary human laws and those whose breach is held to be not only illegal but also an offence against a supernatural power and particularly against Ala, the land" (Green, 1954:99-100).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: "Legal rules are of two main classes and are recognised as such. There are those which might be called ordinary human laws and those whose breach is held to be not only illegal but also an offence against a supernatural power and particularly against Ala, the land" (Green, 1954:99-100).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: "Legal rules are of two main classes and are recognised as such. There are those which might be called ordinary human laws and those whose breach is held to be not only illegal but also an offence against a supernatural power and particularly against Ala, the land. Of the perpetrator of such an offence it would be said 'he polluted the land.' Such offences are usually said to be nsɔ-taboo-and are distinguished from merely natural offences. In many cases they involve a propitiatory rite for Ala in addition to the punishment of the offender" (Green, 1964:99-100).

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a required sacrifice of time.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that ancestral worship is the responsibility of the family or household. It is unclear if this small-scale ritual participation is mandatory "Apart from the performance of certain burial and second-burial ceremonies which are the concern of the whole village, its sphere is that of the individual or extended families rather than of the village as a whole, and does not therefore fall directly within our province, which is the organisation of the village" (Green, 1964:52).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Notes: "The biggest communal rite is known as *irɔ ɔfɔ* or *ɔfala*. It is a thanksgiving ceremony in which the whole community participates. Each community holds the rite on its market day, when elaborate preparations for it are made. Women prepare food and oil beans, children fetch water and wood, and everyone else works to clear the village paths and the marketplace" (Uchendu, 1965:99). "The whole of Agbaja is, moreover, a religious unit in the sense that it possesses a guardian deity served by religious slaves known as *osu*, with its shrine in the village of the senior man of Agbaja. This deity has its male aspect *Ezεala Ɔgθugo*, and its female aspect *Lɔlɔ Ajala*, and has its annual rites. There is also a deity belonging to all Agbaja called *Ɔpara Ogugu*, with its shrine in the central market place. The whole of Agbaja performs rites in its honour annually in the seventh month" (Green, 1964:12).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Igbo have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a petty chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Because there is no formal, centralized head of the main political unit (the village group), the Igbo are more accurately described as a tribe. "There are estimated to be nearly four million Ibo or, more correctly, Ibo-speaking people in South Eastern Nigeria. Mainly on the left bank of the Niger, they reach from the Delta, into which some of them have filtered, up through the flat belt of tropical forest and into the rolling, orchard bush country that lies north of it. Their most immediately striking characteristic is what has aptly been called their social fragmentation. This great people is broken up into hundreds of small, more or less independent, social units, the largest being, in many cases, what we may call the village-group. This is a collection of villages bound together by certain ties, but each one, at any rate in the district with which we are concerned, largely managing its own affairs" (Green, 1964:3). "There is, as we have said, no Ibo State, no central authority which welds the people into a political whole. Thus, having no paramount chief or other organ of government common to them all, they lack what to other peoples may be powerful symbols of unity" (Green, 1964:5). "In this whole discussion as to the location of authority in the Ibo community two things emerge clearly; we see that in each separate side of life, whether economic, military, supernatural or legal, there is no concentration of power in any one centre; in intimate relation with this fact we also see that there is in the whole village or village-group community, no one centre of power based, as is the power of the chief among some other peoples, on authority in all these spheres of life. We see, too, that the individual of ability or force of character can make himself felt; so also to some extent can the head of a large family, or a man of wealth" (Green, 1964:138).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: "...children tend to be present at many of the doings of their elders and education is, on the whole, probably a matter of assimilation rather than of formal teaching" (Green, 1964:79).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: A mission-run school is located in the focal village (Green, 1964:29-30).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "The society is politically semi-autonomous, being governed by another society with an alien culture which operates largely through the indigenous political institutions, e.g., through indirect rule, but which requires conformity on major issues such as refraining from war, headhunting, or cannibalism" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 1 Political Autonomy).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 10: Police) Note: Equivalent to SCCS Variable 90.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 9: Judiciary) Note: Equivalent to SCCS Variable 89.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a formal legal code among the Igbo.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Igbo rely almost entirely on extensive/shifting agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Igbo rely almost entirely on extensive/shifting agriculture for subsistence. Animal husbandry supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.